

Foreign Experience of the Legal Socialization of the person

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Abstract:

In this article, we will discuss the development of new and modern directions of legal socialization of the person, their application to the national practice through the comparative-legal analysis of world practice in this area.

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Introduction

It is important to develop new and modern directions of legal socialization of the person, to make comparative-legal analysis of world practice in this area, to apply their positive aspects in the practice of our country.

As Russian scholar Vera Babaskina has rightly acknowledged, in the current globalization of the legal socialization of a person, the factors influencing it cannot be limited to the territory of a particular state. The greater the influence of national customs, family, and social environment on the legal socialization of individuals, the greater the influx of information from foreign countries under the influence of globalization [1].

Legal socialization of a person is a process that is largely influenced by socialization agents. Based on this, it is necessary to analyze foreign experience more closely related to the nature of socialization agents. Because a person has the same biological structure. Wherever a person is born in the west, east, south, or north, he or she will experience socialization as a human being. However, the factors that influence its maturity are many. These are the factors that play an important role in the legal socialization of a person.

When focusing on international experience of legal socialization, it is advisable to compare the common practice of countries with more national, ethnic, and regional differences. The foreign practice of legal socialization of a person shows that there is a difference between the West and the East.

First of all, we will focus on the experience of eastern countries. "Recently, a number of scientific and practical studies related to the study of psycho-pedagogical regularities of personality socialization in the eastern countries and the identification of the factors influencing them and their psychological characteristics have been carried out. The present research is devoted to identifying and studying the characteristics of education and upbringing as factors that influence the development and success of a child's personality. Research shows that in the east, parents, family members, relatives, and the community as a whole have an impact on the legal socialization of individuals" [2].

In Western countries, research on the legalization of personality is influenced by the fact that a person is more than a community person, a role model. In Western countries, because of the weaker influence of the community, the individual strives for individuality and thereby perfection.

According to Western Scholars J.Piaget and R.Mertons, legal socialization of a person is carried out in two interrelated directions: adaptation (social cultural experience, culture assimilation) and individualization (independence, relative identity) [3]. Of course, these are subjective considerations. But such trends in the legal socialization of the individual are equally applicable to both eastern and western countries.

Main part

Foreign experience of legalization of the person shows that the legal socialization of a person has a special influence on the legal education of young people in different countries, current legislation and legal practice. In addition, the specificity, territorial location, climate, lifestyle and lifestyle of people, their relationships, traditions, national values within each state are also important in the legal socialization of the individual [4].

In the Russian Federation, there has been a number of scientific studies on the impact of personal example on the legalization of personality. Having done research on this issue, Ms. Kosimova notes that there are some common differences between imitation and imitation along with many common aspects. When a particular individual strives to live in a legal, culturally competent person, he tries to imitate his actions in the same way. When these differences are reflected in the context of action and activity, their similarity is only due to the positive purpose [5].

If we look at the factors that influence the legalization of personality in foreign countries, the impact of legal practice also has on legal socialization. For example, the Russian Federal Legislature (Gosduma) is currently considering an amendment to the Criminal Code to further reduce the age of criminal liability. According to it, the age of criminal liability is reduced to 12 years. The initiators of the law explain the main reason for the increase in the number of juvenile delinquency and crime in the country.

The media has a great influence on the legalization of personality. If you look at the figures, only 4% of the southern states have computers, 75% of the phones are in the 9 richest countries. Japan alone has more phones than 50 African countries. There are no newspapers in 39 developing countries, and only 30 in one. There are currently 125 daily newspapers in Japan, with 1687 in the United States.

The Internet, which is a breakthrough in modern science, with its convenience, is at the forefront of adversely affecting young minds. In addition to grifting on the internet, there are

many other risks for teenagers. That is, with the ever-increasing problem of children and the Internet, it is important to remember that virtual websites are open to access to extremist sites and associations. The curious nature of children leads them to the aforementioned types of sites, causing them to view information that poses a threat to their mental or physical health. E-mail messages can have a powerful psychological effect and encourage children to commit crime both inside and outside the Internet. Young people who know bank or credit card accounts have the opportunity to buy online cars, from small toys to the latest in online shopping. This makes them the target of virtual fraudsters.

The task of these new professionals is to create an open and secure information space that will introduce a culture of Internet use in the family and will not cause psychological, spiritual and physical harm to children. The Internet Content Assessment Association (ICRA) is an independent international organization whose mission is to warn parents about the unpleasant and dangerous relationships that await their children on the network, to protect children from cybercrime and free speech. Suberangels - the first European body to protect the rights of children on the Internet, was founded in 1995 and is currently a member of the United States and Canada. As the problems deepen, such organizations are also intensifying their extensive research and development of response to existing threats. In particular, a survey conducted by Save the Children found that 85 percent of US teenagers aged 15-17 and 93 percent of Canadian youth regularly use the Internet. According to a study by the Association for Research in Communication Media, adolescents have left adults in the Internet in 2004.

A study by the Spanish Child Protection Agency found that 44% of children who regularly use the Internet have been harassed at least once during virtual communication, and 11% repeatedly. It is noteworthy that 14.5% of surveyed youths have had meetings with strangers on the Internet, 10% of them have gone to such meetings alone, and 7% have never told anyone about it. Around the world, 38% reported that they regularly watch websites for child abuse, and 26% regularly report websites that are nationalistic. In the last months of 2008, Microsoft, one of the world's most popular companies, announced that it will close its chat rooms in 28 countries. The move has been fully supported by law enforcement and charitable organizations dealing with child issues, as free and uncontrolled forum rooms have become a source of spam, viruses and immoral information. As a result, MSN's free chats have stopped operating in many countries in Europe, the Middle East, Africa, Asia, and Latin

America. Instead, Microsoft Messenger has introduced an instant messaging system that requires you to sign up to use the service.

Such effects have a great impact on the legal socialization of young people and the individual in general. In this regard, the issue of improvement of legal education will appear again.

Foreign experience analysis of legal socialization of the person has allowed to identify the following directions: firstly, the specific influence of territorial location on the legal socialization of the person, for example: specificity in the eastern and western cultures; secondly, the characteristics, mentality, customs and traditions of each country; thirdly, the impact of socialization agents, in particular on the social environment, family, parent, educational setting, and so on; Fourth, the impact of globalization on the legal socialization of the person, the Internet, the media, modern technology, and so on.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the above factors should be taken into account when creating organizational and methodological frameworks related to legal socialization of the person, with a particular emphasis on legal practice, current lawmaking, legal education and training.

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